

BoostNet-WB: Adaptive Boosting with Neural Network Weak Learners and Weighted Bootstrap Resampling

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Abstract

We present BoostNet-WB, a practical modification of the AdaBoost algorithm that incorporates compact neural networks as weak learners. The method leverages a **weighted bootstrap (WB)** resampling strategy to account for the importance of training examples during stochastic gradient descent, while preserving compatibility with standard loss functions used in modern deep learning libraries. To ensure model convergence and maintain weak learner properties, we introduce dynamically adjustable architectures and regularization techniques that prevent overfitting. Experimental evaluation on various synthetic datasets demonstrates that BoostNet-WB consistently outperforms classical decision stump-based AdaBoost in classification quality, with the adaptive version achieving the best trade-off between performance and training time. The results affirm the viability of neural networks in boosting frameworks and highlight their potential for future ensemble methods.

Keywords: boosting, neural networks, adaptive architecture, overfitting control

1 Introduction

Ensemble learning combines predictions from multiple models to achieve higher accuracy, robustness, and generalization compared to any single model. AdaBoost (Adaptive Boosting) [1] is a popular ensemble technique that constructs a sequence of weak classifiers, where each subsequent model focuses on correcting errors made by previous ones.

Traditionally, AdaBoost uses decision stumps as base learners [2]. However, these models have limited expressiveness, making them suboptimal for complex or high-dimensional tasks. We propose replacing stumps with neural networks—compact yet powerful function approximators—used under constraints to preserve the "weak" nature of base learners.

A key challenge is integrating sample weighting into neural network training, as standard `sample_weight` parameters are often incompatible with stochastic gradient methods. To address this, we use weighted bootstrap resampling [3]: training examples are sampled with replacement according to their importance weights, making the approach compatible with mini-batch SGD.

Our contributions include:

- Introducing weighted bootstrap to model sample importance during neural network training.
- Dynamic architecture adaptation and regularization to maintain weak learner behavior.
- Experimental validation of the proposed method against classical AdaBoost and gradient boosting on diverse synthetic datasets [4].

2 Methodology

2.1 BoostNet-WB Algorithm Overview

BoostNet-WB modifies the classical AdaBoost algorithm as follows:

- Neural networks are used as weak classifiers.
- Sample weights are incorporated via weighted bootstrap resampling rather than loss function modification.

Each boosting iteration consists of:

1. Sampling a training set with weighted bootstrap.
2. Training a neural network on the resampled set.
3. Computing prediction error.
4. Calculating classifier weight and updating sample weights.
5. Normalizing the weights.

The final ensemble prediction is a weighted vote of all neural classifiers.

2.2 Weighted Bootstrap Resampling

Given sample weights w_i at iteration t , the probability of selecting example i is proportional to w_i . A bootstrap sample of size N is generated accordingly.

Advantages:

- Avoids modifying loss functions.
- Compatible with stochastic optimizers.
- Naturally emphasizes hard examples via exponential weight growth over iterations.

2.3 Dynamic Neural Architecture Adaptation

To prevent overfitting, the neural network structure is adjusted dynamically:

- For low-dimensional input ($d \leq 5$): architecture (10, 5).
- For higher dimensions: architecture (64, 32).
- Regularization via L2 penalty ($\alpha = 0.001$) and early stopping (10% validation split).
- Training capped at 500 iterations.

In the adaptive version, the architecture is simplified by 20% every 10 iterations to maintain weak learner capacity [7].

2.4 Convergence Conditions

AdaBoost guarantees exponential error decay if base learners have error < 0.5 and are appropriately weighted [2]. BoostNet-WB ensures this via:

- Architecture regularization.
- Adaptive structure control.
- Weighted bootstrap as an implicit weighting mechanism.

Formally, the empirical bootstrap error approximates the weighted classification error, enabling theoretical guarantees to hold.

2.5 Algorithm Pseudocode

Algorithm 1: BoostNet-WB: Boosting Neural Networks via Weighted Bootstrap Resampling

Input: Training data (X, y) , number of rounds T , initial architecture \mathcal{A}_0
Output: Ensemble of classifiers $\{f_t\}_{t=1}^T$ with weights $\{\alpha_t\}_{t=1}^T$

```
1 Initialize sampling weights  $w_i \leftarrow \frac{1}{N}$  for all  $i$ 
2  $\mathcal{A} \leftarrow \mathcal{A}_0$  // Initial neural net architecture
3 for  $t \leftarrow 1$  to  $T$  do
4   Sample  $N$  examples from  $(X, y)$  with replacement according to  $w_i$  // Weighted bootstrap
5   Train neural network  $f_t$  on resampled set using architecture  $\mathcal{A}$ 
6   Evaluate  $\varepsilon_t = \sum w_i \cdot \mathbb{1}[f_t(x_i) \neq y_i]$  on full dataset // Weighted error used for  $\alpha_t$ 
7   if  $\varepsilon_t \geq 0.5$  then
8     | Skip round
9   end
10  Compute classifier weight:  $\alpha_t \leftarrow \frac{1}{2} \log\left(\frac{1-\varepsilon_t}{\varepsilon_t}\right)$ 
11  Update weights:  $w_i \leftarrow w_i \cdot e^{\alpha_t \cdot \mathbb{1}[f_t(x_i) \neq y_i]}$  for all  $i$ 
12  Normalize:  $w_i \leftarrow w_i / \sum w_i$ 
13  if adaptive architecture and  $t$  is a multiple of 10 then // every 10 rounds, empirically chosen
14    | Reduce size of  $\mathcal{A}$  by factor (e.g., 0.8)
15  end
16 end
17 return  $\{f_t, \alpha_t\}_{t=1}^T$ 
```

3 Experiments

3.1 Datasets

Three synthetic datasets were used:

- **Linear:** linearly separable ($n = 2000, d = 10$).
- **Moons:** nonlinear two-moons (noise = 0.3).
- **Circles:** concentric circles (noise = 0.2).

3.2 Compared Models

- **AdaBoost + Decision Stumps**
- **BoostNet-WB (Fixed):** fixed (64, 32) architecture.
- **BoostNet-WB (Adaptive):** structure simplified every 10 iterations.
- **Gradient Boosting Classifier (GBDT)**

Training/test split: 70/30. Evaluation metrics include accuracy, F1-score, AUC-ROC, and training time [8].

3.3 Results Summary

Dataset	Model	Accuracy	F1	AUC	Time (s)
Linear	AdaBoost Stump	0.7417	0.7471	0.8218	0.09
	BoostNet-WB Fixed	0.9417	0.9418	0.9846	8.50
	BoostNet-WB Adaptive	0.9433	0.9439	0.9825	6.91
	GBDT	0.7967	0.7993	0.8879	0.17
Moons	AdaBoost Stump	0.8883	0.8914	0.9651	0.05
	BoostNet-WB Fixed	0.8967	0.8970	0.9681	5.29
	BoostNet-WB Adaptive	0.9000	0.8993	0.9676	1.86
	GBDT	0.9017	0.9028	0.9661	0.05
Circles	AdaBoost Stump	0.8633	0.8723	0.9443	0.05
	BoostNet-WB Fixed	0.8817	0.8846	0.9523	4.70
	BoostNet-WB Adaptive	0.8883	0.8918	0.9513	1.75
	GBDT	0.8700	0.8754	0.9463	0.05

Table 1: Comparison of model performance and training time (in seconds) across datasets.

3.4 Training Dynamics Visualization

To better understand the behavior of BoostNet-WB during training, we visualize the classifier errors, accuracy, F1-score, and AUC-ROC over boosting rounds for each dataset. Figures 1, 2, and 3 illustrate the metrics for the Linear, Moons, and Circles datasets, respectively.

Figure 1: Training dynamics on the **Linear** dataset: classifier errors, accuracy, F1-score, and AUC-ROC over iterations.

Figure 2: Training dynamics on the **Moons** dataset.

Figure 3: Training dynamics on the **Circles** dataset.

4 Discussion

BoostNet-WB addresses the incompatibility of neural networks with standard AdaBoost weighting by introducing a sampling-based solution. Empirical evidence supports the method’s efficacy across data types, particularly on complex or nonlinear distributions. Earlier studies [5, 6] highlight the challenges of combining neural networks with standard AdaBoost weighting, motivating the sampling-based strategy in BoostNet-WB.

Adaptive architecture tuning prevents overfitting while maintaining ensemble convergence. Despite higher training cost (especially on CPU), the gains in performance and flexibility justify the approach.

5 Conclusion

BoostNet-WB expands the boosting paradigm by integrating neural networks as weak learners via weighted bootstrap. This preserves core principles of AdaBoost while enhancing model expressiveness. The approach shows promise for further development, including deep architectures, convolutional/recurrent components, and real-world scalability.

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